

SAPIENZA
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**Effects of autonomous Ridepooling on traffic
performance - An agent-based simulation using
MATsim**

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1. Introduction

Sharing rides is a long-running custom that exists even in very old times while traveling was by horse and buggy. However, current innovations make sharing a ride simpler, more accessible, and more efficient. Modern mobility services based on pooling, picking up several riders into the same vehicle, can decrease travel expenses, alleviate congestion, and reduce greenhouse gas emissions. Furthermore, they offer travelers additional mobility options between the traditional car ownership and public transit[1].

The main motivations for pooling are economical and environmental benefits[1]. Cars are among the primary underutilized capital resources in economy, sitting empty most of the time and typically carrying merely one person the rest of the time[1]. If cars were used more regularly, and if they carried two, three, or more travelers, their cost per rider, and per hour, would decrease considerably. But the pooling advantages go beyond cheaper mobility. If the car carries many people who might otherwise drive themselves, sharing would be able to result in fewer vehicles on the road, which implies less air pollution and energy consumption and fewer greenhouse gas emissions and parking spaces[1]. The potential for significant reductions in pollution and greenhouse gas emissions is enormous given that there are more than one billion cars and light trucks worldwide. [1].

It is known that technologically, a future with many shared rides is now possible. Uber and Lyft, two companies that offer ridesharing and ridepooling services, are growing in popularity and competing with traditional taxis. The market's future could also be drastically altered by the advent of autonomous vehicles, especially from an economic standpoint. In recent years, as the population has grown, there have been a rising number of private cars on the road, which has led to several issues like traffic jams, stress, air pollution, and noise pollution.

In this work by using MATsim, it will be examined how much the number of private cars in Karlsruhe in Germany could be reduced by replacing them with autonomous ridepooling system and check the effects of this replacement on other parameters like average travel time of people and total driven distance by vehicles.

2. Agent based simulations

Over the past few decades, there have repeatedly been significant changes to personal mobility and transportation. Computer simulations can be used to foresee, evaluate, and support decision-making for transportation planners and authorities.

Traffic simulators can be classified based on their modelling approach and they are divided into following levels of detail[2],[3]:

1. Macroscopic simulations concentrate on modeling traffic flow using complex mathematical models. This kind of simulation can be used for wide-area system analysis where detailed modeling is not necessary, such as the simulation of highway traffic. Macroscopic simulations are relatively quick and use less computational power because of the low degree of precision.
2. Individual entities are modeled in great detail in microscopic simulations. Travelers, vehicles, traffic signals, etc., are examples of potential entities. Urban traffic studies frequently makes use of this kind of simulation. Analysis of the system's macro and micro elements (such as the multimodal traffic, traffic light algorithms) is feasible. Therefore, it is possible that microscopic simulations will take more time to compute.
3. Mesoscopic simulations combine macroscopic and microscopic simulation models. In comparison to macroscopic techniques, traffic entities are more precisely modeled, but it seems that individual interactions and behaviors are less accurately captured.

4. Even more specific than microscopic methods are nanoscopic simulations. This kind of simulation is used in the field of autonomous driving, where it is necessary to investigate internal car processes including gear shifting and vehicle vision.

Agent-based models can be thought of as microscopic simulations with a higher level of detail that can also be utilized for research.

3. Introducing MATsim

MATSim is an open-source, multi-agent simulation software framework that is activity-based and extendable. It is available for download from the internet. The framework is created for large-scale scenarios. Kai Nagel's desire to advance his work led him to launch the MATSim project at ETH Zürich, Swiss Federal Institute of Technology. In 2004 After his departure to TU Berlin, Berlin Institute of Technology, Kay W. Axhausen joined the team and brought a unique perspective and experience[4].

Integral microscopic simulation of the resulting traffic flows and the congestion they cause is performed by MATSim. By following the daily schedule and the choices made by the synthetic travelers, it employs a microscopic description of demand. This can be described as "agent-based" in hindsight. It quickly runs microscopic simulations with 10^7 or more "particles" and optimizes the experienced utility of the entire schedule through the coevolutionary search for the resulting equilibrium or steady state[4].

For example, a queue-based model is used in the network loading simulation, neglecting the extremely complex and computationally expensive car-following behavior. It is made to simulate a single day, which serves as the standard analytical unit for activity-based models. A multi-day model might, however, be used in theory[4].

It is built on the co-evolutionary theory. While competing for space-time slots with all other agents on the transportation system, each agent repeatedly optimizes its daily activity schedule[4].

3.1. Basic Functionality

MATSim operates like a repetitive non-cooperative game in which each agent seeks to maximize their utility. Agents have the ability to alter their behavior and adjust to new situations in every iteration of the (same) game. Each action an agent takes has an effect on other agents, their experiences, and their behavior.

A MATSim run contains a configurable number of iterations, represented by the loop in [4, Fig. 1].

Figure 1. MATSim loop, also called the MATSim cycle.

All agents start off with a daily schedule that includes a variety of activities at set locations along with information regarding the mode of transportation that will be utilized to go between them. There are numerous methods to travel these routes (car, public transport, on foot, by bike and others). As shown in Figure 1, after this demand is generated on a specific network, it is then implemented and adjusted in an iterative process.

The initial daily plans are simulated after MATSim has processed all of the data. At the end of the day, an evaluation is conducted using the specified criteria. Good plans are preserved, while agents with lower scores are permitted to alter their plans by selecting an alternative route, mode of transportation, time, or destination.

Following the rescheduling, a new simulation of all agent plans' interactions is run. These iteration processes may be repeated a number of times, depending on the situation. The

replanning step is skipped in the last iterations, and just the agents' plans that match the best are simulated in order to achieve optimal benefit for everyone.

Each step of the loop is explained in the following sections.

3.1.1. Initial Demand

The research area's population's daily activity chains generate the initial demand. In MATSim, the modeled people are referred to as agents. MATSim employs an activity-based approach, which means that people travel because they want to do an activity that they can't do at their current location, in contrast to standard trip-based demand models. Each person plans a variety of daily activities (such as time spent at home, shopping, or working)[4].

Possible sources for initial plans are Travel diaries, Mobile phone data, Senozon method and Synthetic generation by other means.

More details of the components of the input data of the population is explained in the next chapters.

3.1.2. Mobsim

Mobsim is abbreviation for the mobility simulation. All plans are carried out simultaneously by Mobsim in a simulation of the physical world. In every iteration, each agent chooses a plan from its memory before the MATSim simulates the network loading. This choice is determined by the plan scores, which are calculated following each mobsim run depending on the results of the performed plans[4].

Due to the fact that MATSim is intended for large-scale scenarios, it utilizes the computationally effective queue-based strategy shown in [4, Fig. 2].

Figure 2. Traffic flow model.

When a vehicle enters a network link (a road segment) from an intersection, it is added to the end of the waiting queue. It stays there until the period has passed for using the link with no restrictions, until the person is at the head of the waiting list, and until the next link opens to entry. The method is highly effective, but it obviously comes with a lower level of resolution, thus effects from cars following are not captured. It is assigned as Qsim in the configuration file. QSim is time-step based. The two link parameters, storage capacity and flow capacity serve as a robust foundation for the MATSim traffic flow model. The number of automobiles that can fit into a network link is determined by storage capacity. A link's flow capacity describes how many people can depart it in one time step, or its outflow capacity. It is a unique characteristic of the link.[4].

In addition to the two internal mobsims: QSim, that is set by default, and JDEQSim (Java Discrete Event Queue Simulation); external mobility simulations can be plugged in. For computational reasons, JDEQSim combines the waiting-queue approach with an event-based update step[4]. More details of JDEQSim can be found in MATsim official book.

Every simulation-related event, such as the beginning of an activity or the changing of a network link, is recorded as a MATSim event; see [5, Fig. 3]. Each event has one or multiple attributes. The ID of the agent responsible for initiating the event or the link ID where it took place could also be included. A crucial basis for post-analyses, such as visualizers, is the events file[5].

Figure 3. Mobsim events.

3.1.3. Scoring

Every agent learns by keeping multiple plans, which are scored by executing them in the mobsim, and selecting one based on the score—sometimes with modifications. A score is computed for each executed plan during the scoring phase based on how the strategy actually performed in the synthetic reality[6]. Charypar and Nagel developed the first and most fundamental MATSim scoring function, which was largely based on the Vickrey model for traffic congestion[6]. The following descriptions are taken directly from the MATsim book.

For the basic function, utility of a plan S_{plan} is computed as the sum of all activity utilities $S_{act,q}$ plus the sum of all travel (dis)utilities $S_{trav,mode(q)}$ [6]:

$$S_{plan} = \sum_{q=0}^{N-1} S_{act,q} + \sum_{q=0}^{N-1} S_{trav,mode(q)}$$

With N as the number of activities. Trip q is the trip that follows activity q . For scoring, the last activity is merged with the first activity to produce an equal number of trips and activities.

The utility of an activity q is calculated as follows [6]:

$$S_{act,q} = S_{dur,q} + S_{wait,q} + S_{late.ar,q} + S_{early.dp,q} + S_{short.dur,q}$$

$S_{dur,q}$ is the utility of performing activity q , where opening times of activity locations are taken into account.

$S_{wait,q}$ denotes waiting time spent, for example, in front of a still-closed store.

$S_{late.ar,q}$ specifies the late arrival penalty.

$S_{early.dp,q}$ defines the penalty for not staying long enough.

$S_{short.dur,q}$ is the penalty for a 'too short' activity.

And Travel disutility for a leg q is given as [6]:

$$S_{trav,q} = C_{mode(q)} + \beta_{trav,mode(q)} \cdot t_{trav,q} + \beta_m \cdot \Delta m_q + (\beta_{d,mode(q)} + \beta_m \cdot \gamma_{d,mode(q)}) \cdot d_{trav,q} + \beta_{transfer} \cdot x_{transfer,q}$$

This equation is the direct utility contribution of travel.

where:

$C_{,ode(q)}$ is a mode-specific constant.

$\beta_{trav,mode(q)}$ is the direct marginal utility of time spent traveling by mode. Since MATSim uses and scores 24-hour episodes, this is in addition to the marginal utility of time as a resource.

$T_{trav,q}$ is the travel time between activity locations q and $q+1$.

β_m is the marginal utility of money (normally positive).

Δm_q is the change in monetary budget caused by fares, or tolls for the complete leg (normally negative or zero).

$\beta_{d,mode(q)}$ is the marginal utility of distance (normally negative or zero).

$\gamma_{d,mode(q)}$ is the mode-specific monetary distance rate (normally negative or zero).

$d_{trav,q}$ is the distance traveled between activity locations q and $q+1$.

$\beta_{transfer}$ are public transport transfer penalties (normally negative).

$x_{transfer,q}$ is a 0/1 variable signaling whether a transfer occurred between the previous and current leg.

Note that distance contributes to disutility in two ways. First, it is included in a direct manner via $\beta_{d,mode(q)}$, which is normal for modes involving physical effort, like walking or cycling. Second, distance is also included monetarily via $\beta_m \cdot \gamma_{d,mode(q)}$, which is normal for car or pt mode, where monetary costs increase depending on distance.

Figure [6, Fig. 4] illustrates the scoring function.

Figure 4. Illustration of the scoring function. Top: Individual contributions of activities and legs. Bottom: Score accumulation over a day.

Time runs from left to right. The example shows part of an executed schedule, with home, work, and lunch activities, connected by a car and walk leg. The MATSim mobsim typically starts at midnight and runs until all plans have reached their final activity. By itself, the mobsim, is not limited to a day. However, as already stated the standard scoring function assumes that plans “wrap around” to 24-hour days [6].

The current MATSim default values are [6]:

β_m	=	1	<i>utils/monetaryunit</i>
β_{dur}	=	6	<i>utils/h</i>
$\beta_{trav,mode(q)}$	=	-6	<i>utils/h</i>
β_{wait}	=	0	<i>utils/h</i>
$\beta_{short.dur}$	=	0	<i>utils/h</i>
$\beta_{late.ar}$	=	-18	<i>utils/h</i>
$\beta_{early.dp}$	=	0	<i>utils/h</i> .

The score S that is computed according to the rules given in this section is not assigned directly to the plan, rather, it is exponentially smoothed according to [6]:

$$S^k = \alpha S + (1 - \alpha) S^{k-1}$$

where S^k is the newly memorized score, S^{k-1} is the previously memorized score, S is the score obtained from the plan’s execution in the mobsim, and α is a “learning” or “blending” parameter.

For many situations, both practical and theoretical, it is desirable that each plan’s score converges to its expectation value. Previous equation will not achieve that; it just dampens the fluctuations. A well-known approach to force convergence to the expectation value is MSA (Method of Successive Averages)[6]:

$$S^m = \frac{1}{m} S + \frac{m-1}{m} S^{m-1}$$

This resembles previous equation, with two important differences: (1) The fixed blending parameter α is now replaced by a variable $1/m$, and (2) m is not the iteration number but counts how often a plan was executed and thus scored. This is necessary in MATSim since a plan is not executed and scored in every iteration.

More details on scoring can be read in MATsim official book.

3.1.4. Replanning

The agent-based approach's core is that agents are capable of learning from their prior experiences. MATSim typically permits some agents to modify their plans in several choice dimensions at the start of each iteration. Those include Route choice, Mode choice, Time of day choice and Location choice.

There are some steps involved in replanning. [6]:

1. If an agent has more plans than the maximum number of plans (a configuration parameter), then plans are removed according to a (configurable) plan selector (choice set reduction, plans removal).
2. For some agents, a plan is copied, modified and then selected for the next iteration (choice set extension, innovation).
3. All other agents choose between their plans (choice).

The plans an agent makes in a certain iteration are sometimes referred to as the agent's decision set in that iteration. As a result, steps 1 and 2 of replanning modify the choice set, while step 3 actually executes the option selection. The score is often used to make decisions; plans with higher scores are more likely to be chosen.

"Bad" plans should be eliminated during the plans removal step, "good" plans should be produced during the innovation step, and good plans should be generally chosen during the choice step. In this context, "good" refers to the ability to achieve a high score in mobsim/scoring[6].

Replanning strategies are typically disabled after a certain number of iterations, at which agents will only be able to select from existing plans for some more iterations.

The co-evolutionary process eventually results in a stochastic user equilibrium where no individual agent may adjust its strategy on its own to obtain a higher score a representation of that is shown in [4, Fig. 5].

Figure 5. Typical score progress in MATsim.

3.1.5. Analyses

Normally, the analyses come after the simulation. This is accomplished by using events that are written out at the conclusion of the simulation (and/or in between iterations), which enables several modules to separately assess the simulation results.

The output data are e.g. score statistics, travel distance statistics, leg durations and etc. which are located in the output folder after the simulation.

Events can also be visualized with the help of the program Via which is developed by the company Simunto.

4. How to work with MATsim

In general working with MATsim has different levels. First, it is necessary to install the required software, then prepare input data for simulation, after that acquire the output results and finally the visualization step. The structure of these levels is shown in the Figure 6 and in the next sections they are explained in more details.

Figure 6. MATsim structure.

4.1. Installation

As it was mentioned in previous sections, MATsim is an open-source Java based software. It can be downloaded from MATsim official website¹, or Github². Currently the MATsim version 14 is published and used in this work.

To work with MATsim an Integrated Development Environment (IDE)³ for Java is required and, in this work, “IntelliJ IDEA Community Edition 2022.1.2” is used as development environment, also it is possible to use Eclipse as development environment but the decision on choosing which of these two is up to the user.

¹ <https://www.matsim.org/>

² <https://github.com/matsim-org/>

³ <https://www.jetbrains.com/idea/download/>

In order to run MATsim, Java is required and in the running system for this work the Java SE 17⁴ is used and it can be downloaded directly in IntelliJ. The corresponding section is File, Project Structure.

After downloading the MATsim source code, it should be added as Maven new project.

To add a project as Maven the downloaded source code from GitHub is required. Firstly, a new project as Maven should be created in IntelliJ and then the existing data from source code should be replaced in the created folder and then Maven project should be reloaded. More detailed information about this process can be found in instructions in IntelliJ support website⁵.

The environment in IntelliJ IDE roughly looks like below:

Figure 7. IntelliJ IDE environment.

⁴ <https://jdk.java.net/17/>

⁵ <https://www.jetbrains.com/help/idea/maven-support.html>

The three main elements of the MATSim cycle, execution, scoring, and replanning, operate on what is essentially an in-memory, object-oriented data base of Person objects[5].

The object-oriented programming (OOP) is principally a programming designing methodology that organizes software design around objects or data rather than functions and logic. The organization of an object-oriented program also makes the method beneficial to collaborative development, where projects are divided into groups [7]. The structure, or building blocks, of object-oriented programming include [7]: Classes, Objects, Methods and Attributes.

Alternatively, MATsim can be run by double-clicking the MATSim JAR (Java ARchive) file, GUI⁶ from jar file, and insert the configuration file. The interface is shown in Figure 8:

Figure 8. MATsim GUI.

⁶ Graphical user interface

4.2. Input data

Most MATSim input files are encoded in XML⁷ format. A basic MATsim simulation requires at least three files, a network file, a population file and a configuration file. For more complex simulations like ridepooling scenario, it is necessary to use other extensions and also extra input data like number of vehicles that are distributed in the network and their capacity, number of available seats.

Basic input data for MATsim are explained in next sections and more data on ridepooling scenario is explained in the next chapters.

4.2.1. Network file

Network is the infrastructure that agents (or vehicles) can move around. The network consists of nodes and links. A simple network description in MATSim's XML data format contains the following information[8] and some sections of the Network file are shown in Figures 9 and 10 and the whole file contains much more data and contains thousands of rows. The following descriptions are taken directly from the MATsim book.

A network consists of nodes and links. Each element has an identifier id.

Nodes are described by an x and a y coordinate value.

Links have more features; the from and to attributes reference nodes and describe network geometry. Additional attributes describe traffic-related link aspects:

- The length of the link, typically in meters.

⁷ Extensible Markup Language

- The flow capacity of the link, i.e., number of vehicles that traverse the link, typically in vehicles per hour.
- The free speed is the maximum speed that vehicles are allowed to travel along the link, typically in meters per second.
- The number of lanes (permlanes) available in the direction specified by the 'from' and 'to' nodes.
- The list of modes allowed on the link. This is a comma separated list, e.g., modes="car, bike, taxi".
- All links are uni-directional. If a road can be traveled in both directions, two links must be defined with reversed to and from attributes

Also, that is to mention in MATsim, coordinates should be in Cartesian format.

```

<nodes>
  <node id="10000478228" x="4238323.051274676" y="5437930.939245576" >
  </node>
  <node id="10000478238" x="4237795.085935414" y="5437804.730160378" >
  </node>
  <node id="10005035578" x="4236950.121608161" y="5431167.288108985" >
  </node>
  <node id="10005035579" x="4236945.802529299" y="5431168.116690268" >
  </node>
  <node id="10005035580" x="4236925.187916182" y="5431183.980087508" >
  </node>
  <node id="10006036879" x="4231842.790002088" y="5437705.895563966" >
  </node>
  <node id="10008262929" x="4233702.296035413" y="5436789.73949749" >
  </node>
  <node id="10008774823" x="4241158.180079962" y="5435609.257597643" >
  </node>
  <node id="10008774843" x="4241133.795190384" y="5435618.930826238" >
  </node>
  <node id="10008774856" x="4241132.675264124" y="5435646.448913595" >

```

Figure 9. A section of MATsim Network file, Nodes.

```

<link id="4863" from="10000478228" to="14959809" length="9.38665821307378" freespeed=
"16.666666666666668" capacity="1000.0" permlanes="1.0" oneway="1" modes="car" >
  <attributes>
    <attribute name="osm:relation:route" class="java.lang.String">bus</attribute>
    <attribute name="osm:way:highway" class="java.lang.String">secondary</attribute>
    <attribute name="osm:way:id" class="java.lang.Long">30906552</attribute>
    <attribute name="osm:way:lanes" class="java.lang.String">2</attribute>
    <attribute name="osm:way:name" class="java.lang.String">Theodor-Heuss-Allee</attribute>
  </attributes>
</link>
<link id="48630" from="15432600" to="1457321305" length="12.027562303297296" freespeed=
"8.333333333333334" capacity="600.0" permlanes="1.0" oneway="1" modes="car" >
  <attributes>
    <attribute name="osm:way:highway" class="java.lang.String">residential</attribute>
    <attribute name="osm:way:id" class="java.lang.Long">3453091</attribute>
    <attribute name="osm:way:name" class="java.lang.String">Bonner Straße</attribute>
  </attributes>
</link>

```

Figure 10. A section of MATsim Network file, Links.

4.2.2. Population file

The agents' daily plans explain the MATSim travel demand. Population.xml is a file that contains information about the entire population of agents. In MATSim, plans.xml is also frequently used as an alternative because the population file simply contains a list of daily plans [8].

The data are organized hierarchically in the population. Each person in the population has a list of plans, and each of those plans has a list of actions and legs[8].

Each plan includes a list of activities and legs that detail each agent's intended course of action. Activities are assigned a type and typically have, except for the last activity in a daily plan, a defined end time. An activity is either given a coordinate by being given an x and y attribute value, or it is given a link, specifying from which link the activity may be reached, to indicate the location where the action takes place. Each leg must have a designated transport mode. A leg explains how an agent intends to move from one site to the next. Immediately following the conclusion of the prior action (or leg), an agent begins a new leg[8]. A section of Population file roughly looks like Figure 11 and the main Population file contains much more data and can contain thousands of rows:

```

<person id="65">
  <plan selected="yes" score="93.2987721">
    <activity type="home" x="4239251.498" y="5437827.829" end_time="09:58:00" >
    </activity>
    <leg mode="drt">
    </leg>
    <activity type="work" x="4234857.796" y="5442833.79" end_time="17:58:00" >
    </activity>
    <leg mode="drt">
    </leg>
    <activity type="shopping" x="4234436.417" y="5436761.098" end_time="18:58:00" >
    </activity>
    <leg mode="drt">
    </leg>
    <activity type="home" x="4239251.498" y="5437827.829" >
    </activity>
  </plan>
</person>

```

Figure 11. A section of MATsim Population file, plans of a single person.

4.2.3. Configuration file

Configuration file is also in XML format and it is entry point for a MATSim run. It contains:

- File locations for network and population files.
- The number of iterations to run.
- The length of a simulated day.
- Possible activity start and end times.
- Flow and storage capacity factors.
- And etc.

MATSim uses a modular approach, but a “module” is not a very specific term⁸; thus, In a software framework, modules can be found at several levels. Also, in MATSim a range

⁸ According to the Merriam-Webster (<http://www.merriam-webster.com>), a module is “one of a set of parts that can be connected or combined to build or complete something” or more specifically “a part of a computer or computer program that does a particular job”.

of different functionality types, such as config functions, replanning components, contributions, or even external tools,⁹ are sometimes described as modules. In a metaphorical sense, a module can be thought of as the biggest common factor of all the functionality offered by MATSim [9].

Some of the modules of Configuration file are explained in the next paragraphs and descriptions are taken from the MATsim book.

First module is “Controler”. The MATSim run’s output directory, its number of iterations and the plans and events output interval and also the expected mobsim can be specified here [10]. A section of this module is represented in Figure 12.

```
<module name="controler" >
  <!-- Compression algorithm to use when writing out data to files. Possible values: [none, gzip, lz4, zst] -->
  <param name="compressionType" value="gzip" />
  <!-- Sets whether graphs showing some analyses should automatically be generated during the simulation. The
  generation of graphs usually takes a small amount of time that does not have any weight in big simulations, but add
  a significant overhead in smaller runs or in test cases where the graphical output is not even requested. -->
  <param name="createGraphs" value="true" />
  <!-- Defines when the scoring functions for the population are created. Default=IterationStarts. Possible values:
  [IterationStarts, BeforeMobsim] -->
  <param name="createScoringFunctionType" value="IterationStarts" />
  <!-- true if at the end of a run, plans, network, config etc should be dumped to a file -->
  <param name="dumpDataAtEnd" value="true" />
  <!-- Default=false. If enabled, the router takes travel times needed for turning moves into account. Cannot be used
  if the (Fast)AStarLandmarks routing or TravelTimeCalculator.separateModes is enabled. -->
  <param name="enableLinkToLinkRouting" value="false" />
  <!-- Default=xml; Specifies the file format for writing events. Currently supported: [xml, pb, json]
  Multiple values can be specified separated by commas (','). -->
  <param name="eventsFileFormat" value="xml" />
  <!-- Default=0. First Iteration of a simulation. -->
  <param name="firstIteration" value="0" />
  <!-- Default=1000. Last Iteration of a simulation. -->
  <param name="lastIteration" value="10" />
  <!-- Defines which mobility simulation will be used. Currently supported: qsim JDEQSim hermes
  Depending on the chosen mobsim, you'll have to add additional config modules to configure the corresponding mobsim.
  For 'qsim', add a module 'qsim' to the config. -->
  <param name="mobsim" value="qsim" />
  <param name="outputDirectory" value="output/drt_door2door" />
  <!-- Possible values: failIfDirectoryExists, overwriteExistingFiles, deleteDirectoryIfExists -->
  <param name="overwriteFiles" value="deleteDirectoryIfExists" />
  <!-- The type of routing (least cost path) algorithm used, may have the values: [Dijkstra, AStarLandmarks,
  FastDijkstra, FastAStarLandmarks, SpeedyALT] -->
  <param name="routingAlgorithmType" value="AStarLandmarks" />
</module>
```

Figure 12. A section of Controler module in MATsim configuration file.

Next module is “Global”. Here the simulation’s random seed, the “global” number of Java threads and the coordinate system can be defined[10]. A section of this module is represented in Figure 13.

⁹ Standalone tools referencing MATSim as a library, such as the network editor, or the visualizer Via.

```

<module name="global" >
  <param name="coordinateSystem" value="EPSG:31468" />
  <param name="defaultDelimiter" value="," />
  <param name="insistingOnDeprecatedConfigVersion" value="true" />
  <!-- "global" number of threads. This number is used, e.g., for replanning, but NOT in QSim. This can typically be
  set to as many cores as you have available, or possibly even slightly more. -->
  <param name="numberOfThreads" value="2" />
  <param name="randomSeed" value="4711" />
</module>

```

Figure 13. A section of Global module in MATsim configuration file.

Next module is “Network”. This module specifies which network file will be used in the simulation[10]. A section of this module is represented in Figure 14.

```

<module name="network" >
  <!-- The Coordinates Reference System in which the coordinates are expressed in the input file. At import, the
  coordinates will be converted to the coordinate system defined in "global", and will be converted back at export. If
  not specified, no conversion happens. -->
  <param name="inputCRS" value="null" />
  <param name="inputChangeEventsFile" value="null" />
  <param name="inputNetworkFile" value="network.xml.gz" />
  <param name="laneDefinitionsFile" value="null" />
  <param name="timeVariantNetwork" value="false" />
</module>

```

Figure 14. A section of Network module in MATsim configuration file.

Another module is “Strategy”. In this section parameters like Innovation shut off, at fraction of iterations where innovative strategies are switched off, and StrategyName where replanning strategies are defined, which can be innovative or selection from previous plans. A section of this module is represented in Figure 15.

```

<module name="strategy" >
  <!-- the external executable will be called with a config file as argument. This is the pathname to a possible
  skeleton config, to which additional information will be added. Can be null. -->
  <param name="ExternalExeConfigTemplate" value="null" />
  <!-- time out value (in seconds) after which matsim will consider the external strategy as failed -->
  <param name="ExternalExeTimeout" value="3600" />
  <!-- root directory for temporary files generated by the external executable. Provided as a service; I don't think
  this is used by MATSim. -->
  <param name="ExternalExeTmpFileRootDir" value="null" />
  <!-- fraction of iterations where innovative strategies are switched off. Something like 0.8 should be good. E.g.
  if you run from iteration 400 to iteration 500, innovation is switched off at iteration 480 -->
  <param name="fractionOfIterationsToDisableInnovation" value="0.8" />
  <!-- maximum number of plans per agent. ``0`` means ``infinity``. Currently (2010), ``5`` is a good number -->
  <param name="maxAgentPlanMemorySize" value="5" />
  <!-- strategyName of PlanSelector for plans removal. Possible defaults: WorstPlanSelector SelectRandom
  SelectExpBetaForRemoval ChangeExpBetaForRemoval PathSizeLogitSelectorForRemoval . The current default,
  WorstPlanSelector is not a good choice from a discrete choice theoretical perspective. Alternatives, however, have
  not been systematically tested. kai, feb'12 -->
  <param name="planSelectorForRemoval" value="WorstPlanSelector" />
  <parameterset type="strategysettings" >
    <!-- iteration after which strategy will be disabled. most useful for ``innovative`` strategies (new routes,
    new times, ...). Normally, better use fractionOfIterationsToDisableInnovation -->
    <param name="disableAfterIteration" value="-1" />
    <!-- path to external executable (if applicable) -->
    <param name="executionPath" value="null" />
    <!-- strategyName of strategy. Possible default names: SelectRandom BestScore KeepLastSelected ChangeExpBeta
    SelectExpBeta SelectPathSizeLogit (selectors),
    ReRouteTimeAllocationMutatorTimeAllocationMutator_ReRouteChangeSingleTripModeChangeTripModeSubtourModeChoice
    (innovative strategies). -->
    <param name="strategyName" value="TimeAllocationMutator" />
    <!-- subpopulation to which the strategy applies. "null" refers to the default population, that is, the set of
    persons for which no explicit subpopulation is defined (ie no subpopulation attribute) -->
    <param name="subpopulation" value="null" />
    <!-- weight of a strategy: for each agent, a strategy will be selected with a probability proportional to its
    weight -->
    <param name="weight" value="0.1" />
  </parameterset>
</module>

```

Figure 15. A section of Strategy module in MATsim configuration file.

Next module is “PlanCalcScore”. This module specifies the parameters used for scoring agents’ plans[10]. As explained in scoring phase in section 3.1.3., the actual performance of the plan in the synthetic reality is taken to compute each executed plan’s score.

A section of this module is represented in Figure 16.

```
<module name="planCalcScore" >
  <parameterset type="activityParams" >
    <param name="activityType" value="work" />
    <param name="closingTime" value="24:00:00" />
    <param name="earliestEndTime" value="undefined" />
    <param name="latestStartTime" value="undefined" />
    <param name="minimalDuration" value="undefined" />
    <param name="openingTime" value="05:00:00" />
    <param name="priority" value="1.0" />
    <param name="scoringThisActivityAtAll" value="true" />
    <param name="typicalDuration" value="08:00:00" />
    <param name="typicalDurationScoreComputation" value="relative" />
  </parameterset>
```

Figure 16. A section from PlanCalcScore module in MATsim configuration file.

There are some other modules in Configuration file like TimeAllocationMutator, Vehicles and etc. which are edited according to different scenarios and if not, they have all default values. More details on Configuration file can be read in chapter 4 of MATsim official book.

4.3. Output data

The analyses results are carried out after the simulation and are put in output folder. This folder contains information like e.g. score statistics, travel distance statistics, leg durations and etc and these data are used to figure out the effects of the synthetic simulations and compare different scenarios. These data are generally CSV¹⁰, Text, PNG¹¹ and XML files. Some examples of these data are shown in the following figures.

Figure 17 shows the computation time of each iteration, in this case 10 iterations, in seconds that consist of mobsim and replanning times.

Figure 17. Computation time per iteration.

Figure 18 is the text file corresponding to DRT customer statistics in ridepooling scenario and it consists of important information about the average waiting times, average travel

¹⁰ Comma-separated values

¹¹ Portable Network Graphics

times and etc. There are also other text files which contain information on total distance driven by vehicles, average travel distance and etc.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
1	runId;iteration;rides;wait_average;wait_max;wait_p95;wait_p75;wait_median;percentage_WT_below_10;								
2	NA;0;49175;357.26;625;578;498;380;99.63;100;920.45;8959.93;7685.57;1277.71;2.84;2850;0.05								
3	NA;1;53306;309.86;998;563;446;302;99.82;100;940.7;8977.85;7574.74;1250.56;2.82;819;0.02								
4	NA;2;53330;309.11;898;564;447;300;99.71;100;941.07;8984.41;7574.38;1250.18;2.82;799;0.01								
5	NA;3;53371;309.29;927;563;446;300;99.77;100;942.45;8991.77;7576.3;1251.74;2.82;774;0.01								
6	NA;4;53489;308.85;927;563;446;299;99.76;100;941.8;8985.83;7580.92;1250.64;2.82;716;0.01								
7	NA;5;53298;308.45;1013;564;445;299;99.76;99.99;941.73;8976.92;7570.75;1250.17;2.82;806;0.01								
8	NA;6;53312;308.9;905;564;445;300;99.72;100;941.93;8979.21;7568.7;1250.83;2.81;806;0.01								
9	NA;7;53427;309.49;909;564;445;300;99.69;100;941.81;8982.85;7573.41;1251.29;2.82;743;0.01								
10	NA;8;53365;309.4;760;564;446;300;99.72;100;941.4;8980.7;7568.23;1250.8;2.81;767;0.01								
11	NA;9;53604;309.3;885;564;445;299;99.67;100;941.74;8978.03;7580.24;1251.03;2.82;653;0.01								
12	NA;10;53580;309.4;831;564;446;301;99.65;100;941.02;8968.24;7565.82;1250.42;2.81;670;0.01								

Figure 18. DRT customers statistics.

Figure 19 represents the Score statistics of the whole simulation. As explained earlier in MATsim the co-evolutionary algorithm eventually leads to a stochastic user equilibrium.

Figure 19. Score Statistics.

Figure 20 represents the difference between initially planned waiting time vs the actual waiting time of the simulation and as can be seen only a few persons faced higher waiting times than expected in this sample simulation. Similar figures exists in output folder containing information on actual travel times, planned travel times and etc.

Figure 20. Waiting times.

Figure 21 represents the number of idle and moving vehicles during different times of the day. As can be seen in this figure, which is an example for ridepooling with fleet size of 3000 vehicles, blue and red area are the number of serving vehicles and the gray area is the number of idle vehicles.

Figure 21. Representation of number of serving and idle vehicles.

The above shown data were some samples and the main output folder contains lots of other data which is not possible to go through all of them in detail in this report and more information can be found in MATsim tutorial book.

4.4. Visualization

After the simulation and by accessing the output folder, not only analyses results can be acquired also they can be used for visualizing the simulation. This is done by Via from Simunto and this software can be downloaded from it's official website¹². Free version of this software is available for download, but it is limited to visualizing 500 agents and is valid for 6 months and it's Educational license, for educational or research use only, that has unlimited features and can be bought for 1000 Euros and that is valid for 12 months.

For visualization of a simulation, generally two files are needed, network file and output events files to be imported to Via. That is to mention for specific scenarios like Emissions, Public Transportation and etc. some other data would be necessary to import to Via.

Some representations of Via are shown in the following figures.

Figure 22. Via Simunto interface.

¹² <https://simunto.com/via/>

Figure 23. A sample simulation visualization in Via.

In Via, many information of the simulation can be found for example information of each node, each link, vehicles driven routes, number of people in the vehicle and etc.

In the Figure 24 some information of a sample link is shown.

Figure 24. Information of a link in Via.

In the Figure 25 number of people that are carried in each vehicle is shown, vehicles occupancies.

Figure 25. Representation of Vehicles occupancies in Via.

There are many more features in Via which can be read from it's user manual¹³.

¹³ <https://www.simunto.com/data/via-1.8.1/via-manual.pdf>

5. Building up Karlsruhe scenario

5.1. Some facts about Karlsruhe

Karlsruhe is a city of the German state Baden-Württemberg and is located in south-west of Germany. In the [11, Fig. 26] the location of the city is represented.

Figure 26. Karlsruhe's location.

Over 39% of the **17,342 hectares** that make up the urban area are municipal properties. The built-up or traffic areas make up about 40% of the urban area. Still dominating are forests (26%) and agricultural land (23%). With a **population of 299,785**, the population density is 1,729 people per square kilometer [12].

The significant proportion of young adults (20–29) who are enrolled in training or education has a significant impact on the age distribution. Despite the rising senior population, the percentage of those 65 and older has barely changed over the past few years and is at 19.1%. (57,271 people). On the other hand, in the last ten years, the

percentage of children and young people under the age of 18 (43,278) has decreased from 14.9% to 14.4%[12].

167,073 registered motor vehicles, including **141,949 passenger cars** and 12,583 motorcycles. On average, there are around **554 passenger cars for every 1,000 people** over the age of 18[12]. Length of paved roads in Karlsruhe in year 2020 has been 1,344 Kilometers in which 780 Kilometers is municipal roads [13].

Karlsruhe has 27 districts, and they are shown in the [12, Fig. 27].

01 Innenstadt-Ost	10 Knielingen	19 Durlach
02 Innenstadt-West	11 Grünwinkel	20 Grötzingen
03 Südstadt	12 Oberreut	21 Stupferich
04 Südweststadt	13 Beiertheim-Bulach	22 Hohenwettersbach
05 Weststadt	14 Weiherfeld-Dammerstock	23 Wolfartsweier
06 Nordweststadt	15 Rüppurr	24 Grünwettersbach
07 Oststadt	16 Waldstadt	25 Palmbach
08 Mühlburg	17 Rintheim	26 Neureut
09 Daxlanden	18 Hagsfeld	27 Nordstadt

Figure 27. Karlsruhe districts.

5.2. Building up MATsim network for Karlsruhe

As mentioned earlier, network file of MATsim is in XML format that consists of nodes and links and they may have different attributes like length of the link, flow capacity of the link and etc. and building such a network has a special process according to the network size and our demand.

The easiest way to build a network file is to get the desired map from OpenStreetMap¹⁴ website and then by using JOSM¹⁵ software convert it to MATsim network. The problem with this method is that is limited to very small areas limited up to 50000 nodes and because our area is higher than this limit, so another method should be used. Another problem with this method is that the output network does not contain public transit data, which for some scenarios would be necessary.

In order to make the network for Karlsruhe firstly it is necessary to acquire the raw OSM map of Karlsruhe so the whole map of Germany can be found from the Geofabrik website¹⁶. But as this map is the whole Germany so our desired area should be cut from that. This step is done by using a java tool called Osmosis¹⁷. In the following figures, map of Karlsruhe taken from Google maps, [11, Fig. 28] and [11, Fig. 29], and acquired map from OpenStreetMap, Figure 30, are represented.

¹⁴ <https://www.openstreetmap.org/>

¹⁵ JOSM is an extensible editor for OpenStreetMap, <https://josm.openstreetmap.de/>

¹⁶ <https://www.geofabrik.de/>

¹⁷ Osmosis is a command line Java application for processing Open Street Map data, <https://github.com/openstreetmap/osmosis>

Figure 28. Map of Karlsruhe taken from Google maps.

Figure 29. Satellite map of Karlsruhe taken from Google maps.

Figure 30. OSM map of Karlsruhe.

Now the raw map needs to be converted into MATsim network file. This step can be done by using another Java tool called PT2MATSim [14].

PT2MATSim is a package to convert OSM map to MATsim network and also by using transit data, it can add transit lines to the network as well. PT2MATSim works in the structure shown in [14, Fig. 31] and the detailed instructions can be read in its GitHub page [14]. A representation of PT2MATsim in IntelliJ is shown in the Figure 32.

Although public transit is not used in this work but building a complete network could be beneficial for the future possible works in that area. For transit data the GTFS data for KVV area is used, which covers a larger area than Karlsruhe and is shown in [15, Fig. 33].

In the conversion process it is necessary to use a cartesian coordinate system and in this work the “EPSG:31468” is used with accuracy of 1 meter.

Figure 31. PT2MATSim structure.

```

45  /**
46  * Reads gtfs files in and converts them to an unmapped
47  * MATSim Transit Schedule (mts). "Unmapped" means stopFacilities are not
48  * referenced to Links and transit routes do not have routes (link sequences).
49  * Creates a default vehicles file as well.
50  * <p/>
51  *
52  * @param args [0] folder where the gtfs files are located (a single zip file is not support
53  * [1] Services from which sample day should be used. One of the following:<br/>
54  * <ul>
55  * <li>date in the format yyyyymmdd</li>
56  * <li>dayWithMostTrips (default)</li>
57  * <li>dayWithMostServices</li>
58  * <li>all</li>
59  * </ul>
60  *
61  * [2] output coordinate system. EPSG:* codes are supported and recommended.
62  * Use 'WGS84' for no transformation (though this may lead to errors with P
63  * [3] output transit schedule file
64  * [4] (optional) output default vehicles file
65  * Calls {@link #run}.
66  */
67  public static void main(final String[] args) {
68      if(args.length == 5) {
69          run(args[0], args[1], args[2], args[3], args[4]);
70      } else if(args.length == 4) {

```

Figure 32. A section of PT2MATsim in IntelliJ.

Wabenplan

Gültig ab 30. Mai 2022

Figure 33. KVV area (Karlsruhe transport association - train and bus).

The output network which is in XML format contains only roads and public transit lines and the other unnecessary data like buildings, trees and etc. from OSM map are removed. In the following figures, a representation of details in: Reality ([11, Fig. 34]), OSM¹⁸ (Figure 35) and MATsim network (Figure 36) are shown.

¹⁸ openstreetmap.org

Figure 34. A part of Karlsruhe shown in Google map satellite.

Figure 35. A part of Karlsruhe shown in OSM map in JOSM.

Figure 36. A part of Karlsruhe as MATsim network shown in Via.

The MATsim network of whole Karlsruhe visualized in Via is shown in the figure 37.

Figure 37. MATsim network of Karlsruhe.

5.3. Building up Population file

In fact, population (or plans) file arises from the study area population’s daily activity chains, that was explained earlier in the section “Initial Demand”.

In this work due to lack of access to people’s daily mobility data, it was decided to build up the model synthetically.

At the first stage it was decided to build daily plans for **25,000 people** by assuming all have driver’s license and own a private car. This number is almost 17 percent of the real population’s number owning passenger cars in Karlsruhe.

Next, **city’s area is divided** into three major parts **according to their land use** which are: **Residential, Working and Shopping areas**. That is to mention in reality in some areas there is a mixture of different activities and this divisions are our assumption. Representation of each of these areas are shown in the Figure 38¹⁹.

Figure 38. Division of city areas into different activities.

¹⁹ Photo taken from: https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Karlsruhe_subdivisions.svg

In the next step different types of activities are defined for each person. Generally, it is assumed people can have three types of plans:

- **Home – Work – Home (10,000 persons):** Leaving Home to Work and later coming back Home again.
- **Home – Work – Shopping – Home (5,000 persons):** Leaving Home to Work and after that, leaving for Shopping and finally coming back Home again.
- **Home – Shopping – Home (10,000 persons):** Leaving Home for Shopping and coming back Home again.

And in total there are **55,000 activities, which mean trips** in this work.

Now **these activities must be distributed during the day. Assumptions are:**

Working activity can start from 5 a.m. and its duration is 8 hours and should finish latest at 24 in the midnight.

Shopping activity can start from 7 a.m. and its duration is 1 hour and can be done until 22 p.m.

The time distribution of the activities is as following:

- For “Home – Work”: 5-6 a.m. (15%), 6-9 a.m. (65%), 9-11 a.m. (7.5%), 11-13 p.m. (7.5%), 13-16 p.m. (5%) and respectively after 8 hours of working people return home.
- For “Home – Shopping”: 7-9 a.m. (65%), 9-12 a.m. (25%), 14-18 p.m. (5%), 18-21 p.m. (5%) and respectively after 1 hour of shopping people return home.
- For “Work – Shopping”: 13-14 p.m. (15%), 14-17 p.m. (70%), 17-21 p.m. (15%) and respectively after 1 hour of shopping people return home.

Time distributions are done by Excel with time steps of 1 minute and then are randomly distributed among the population and finally the Excel file was converted to XML file as input file for MATsim.

A representation of a person of the population in Excel and XML format is shown in the Figure 39.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N
1	Person id	activity	X	Y	End Time	leg mode	activity	X	Y	End Time	leg mode	activity	X	Y
2	1	home	4235661	5436513	8:59:00	drt	work	4240598	5434873	16:59:00	drt	home	4235661	5436513


```

<!-- ===== -->
<person id="1">
  <plan>
    <activity type="home" x="4235660.66" y="5436513.233" end_time="08:59:00" >
    </activity>
    <leg mode="drt">
    </leg>
    <activity type="work" x="4240598.436" y="5434873.25" end_time="16:59:00" >
    </activity>
    <leg mode="drt">
    </leg>
    <activity type="home" x="4235660.66" y="5436513.233" >
    </activity>
  </plan>
</person>
<!-- ===== -->

```

Figure 39. Representation of a person of the population in Excel and XML format.

Final distribution of trips during the day is shown in the Figure 40 and as can be seen there is a peak in the morning and a peak in the afternoon.

Figure 40. Distribution of the trips during the day.

6. Karlsruhe Simulation

6.1. Prerequisite concepts

In recent years the number of shared mobility providers all over the world has been steadily growing and in the predictable future, shared autonomous vehicles (SAVs) may turn driverless services into a flexible, on-demand mass-transport system [16]. Users can either share a ride or a vehicle for example a car or bicycle. One of these shared mobility services is ridepooling (sometimes also called ‘shared ridehailing’ or just ‘ridesharing’)[17].

In this concept there are also other sharing services called carsharing and ridesharing. The differences are explained below[18].

- In carsharing, cars provided by a platform can be used as needed, the vehicle is booked and unlocked via an app, and billing is usually carried out per kilometer or minute.
- Ridesharing, in contrast to taxis, is the use of one’s own car for a ride service. Examples for that are Uber and Lyft that match passengers with drivers of vehicles.
- Ridepooling is different from these forms and several passengers can be transported together in one vehicle, and do not need to have the same pick-up point or the same destination.

Demand responsive transport (DRT), as a form of ridesharing systems, where multiple passengers share a vehicle and users can specify their desired location and time of pick-up and drop-off [19].

MATsim provides multiple extensions like Emissions, DRT and etc. that enhance the functionality with additional features, and they can be found in MATsim's github page²⁰.

In this work in order to model Autonomous ridepooling system in Karlsruhe, the "MATSim – Mobility as a Service" project [20] is used. This project contains a collection of examples to simulate (Autonomous) Mobility as a Service (MaaS) and Mobility on Demand (MoD) in MATSim [20].

DRT can either be used in three different operation modes[20]:

- "door2door" for a service serving passengers from door-to-door.
- "serviceAreaBased" for a door2door service that runs only within a certain area.
- "stopbased" Provides a stop-based DRT services, where passengers need to walk to the first access stop and from the last egress stop.

In this work "door2door" mode is used because our assumption is lower walking distances make the service more attractive to users.

In the simulations it is assumed the vehicles are fully automated and perform all driving tasks in all conditions and no human interaction or attention is required.

Dispatch, every time new request comes in [21]:

- Out of unassigned vehicles, find a vehicle that is "best" for the request.
- Assign vehicle to request.
- Vehicle will (eventually) drive to request, pick up, drive to destination, drop off.
- Becoming unassigned again.

²⁰ <https://github.com/matsim-org/matsim-libs/blob/master/contribs/README.md>

In order to dispatch customers in a shared taxi system, the following prerequisites are assumed [16]:

- The overall time spent on traveling (waiting, boarding and riding) must **not** exceed:

$$t_r = \alpha \cdot t_r^{\text{direct}} + \beta$$

t_r^{direct} is the direct ride time between the origin and destination of request i

$\alpha \geq 1$ and $\beta \geq 0$ are parameters used to model the maximal amount of time loss due to waiting, boarding and possible detours.

- The amount of time the customer is willing to wait for departure is **fixed** to t^{wait} .

Also each stop, whether pickup or drop-off, has a fixed duration of t^{stop} .

Vehicles are managed by a central dispatch system that is responsible for scheduling or rejecting incoming requests.

A request can be rejected (e.g. due to constraints violation) only immediately after submission. Once scheduled, the request is guaranteed to be served (i.e. cannot be rejected later) even if there are delays on the way causing violation of some constraints [16]. The process is represented in [21, Fig. 41].

Figure 41. Ridepooling representation.

Now by having the basic knowledge about DRT systems, the simulations of our two types of scenarios are explained in the next sections.

6.2. Private car scenario

In the first case scenario, the assumption is all people have driver's license and use their own private car lonely for their daily trips and as mentioned earlier there are 25,000 people and 55,000 trips. This scenario is simulated for 10 iterations.

In this case as people use their own car so there is no waiting time and no additional time for looking for parking is considered. A representation of driving route of one of the persons is shown in the Figure 42 and in the Figure 43 as can be seen each vehicles occupancy is 1.

Figure 42. Representation of driving route of one of the persons in Private cars scenario.

Figure 43. Representation of vehicles occupancies in Private cars scenario.

6.3. Ridepooling scenario

In the second case scenario, an imaginary ridepooling provider company is introduced and is assumed people use this service instead of their private cars. To simulate this case different fleet sizes are considered and for each, different parameters are assumed which are explained in the next paragraphs.

In this scenario some assumptions are considered and are mentioned below:

- **Each vehicle**, in our case each van, has a **capacity of 6 seats**.
- Vehicles are fully automated.
- Vehicles are electric with a range of 400 kilometers per charge.
- Service is Door to Door.
- Max wait time (t^{wait}) is 600 seconds (10 minutes).
- Stop duration (t^{stop}) for pickup or drop-off is 60 seconds (1 minute).
- Vehicles are distributed randomly in the city among different links and are set at the beginning of the simulation.
- People cannot change their transport mode.
- Trip requests may be rejected due to constraint explained earlier (overall travel time t_r and maximum waiting time t^{wait} should not exceed their allowed limit, else request will be rejected)
- An innovation strategy is considered and that is Time allocation mutator and each person can change his/her departure time up to 900 seconds (15 minutes). This strategy will be selected with a probability proportional to the weight of 0.1.

- Innovative strategy is switched off after 80% of the iterations (persons choose among their existing plans).
- For each simulation 4 iterations are done. In fact, more iterations are not done because the average best score is not improved considerably even with more iterations and as each iteration is time consuming so 4 iterations is fine in our case.

The above-mentioned assumptions are fixed for all of our ridepooling simulations but there are three important parameters that are different for each of our simulations which are Fleet size, α and β parameters that were explained in Prerequisite concepts section and their values are as following:

- For **Fleet size** 8 different sizes are considered which are **750, 1000, 1250, 1500, 2000, 3000, 5000 and 7000 vehicles**.
- For **α** , 3 different values are considered which are **1.25, 1.5 and 1.75**.
- For **β** , 2 different values are considered which are **600 and 1200 seconds** (10 and 20 minutes).

In total for ridepooling scenario, **48 simulations** are done, and each took almost 90 minutes with a laptop equipped with AMD Ryzen7 5800H series CPU, with 8 Cores and 16 Threads, and 16GB of Memory.

A representation of driving route of one of the vehicles in one of the simulations is shown in the Figure 44 and also some vehicles occupancies in the same simulation are shown in the Figure 45.

Figure 44. Representation of driving route of one of the vehicles in one of the ridepooling simulations.

Figure 45. Representation of vehicles occupancies in one of the ridepooling simulations.

7. Simulation Results

In the previous chapter basic assumptions of our two case scenarios, Private cars and Ridepooling scenarios, and parameters of each simulation, in total 49 simulations, were explained.

After running all simulations, analyses results of each simulation, as explained in the first chapter, are found in its output folder and are explained in the following sections.

7.1. Results for Private cars scenario

Analyses results for this case scenario are shown in the Table 1.

Table 1. Analyses results of Private cars scenario.

Results of Private cars scenario	
Total distance driven (km)	422,007
Mean travel time per trip (seconds)	655
Waiting time (seconds)	0
Mean distance driven by each vehicle (km)	16.8

Distance driven by each vehicle on average is calculated by dividing total distances driven to the total number of vehicles, which is 25,000 in this scenario and as can be seen it is 16.8 Kilometers for each vehicle.

Total travel time per trip on average is 655 seconds (10:55 minutes) and as mentioned earlier no time for looking for a parking spot is considered.

7.2. Results for Ridepooling scenario

Analyses information resulted from all simulations are summarized in the following tables and each column is explained in detail in the next sections. In the Table 2 all summarized data are shown together and in Table 3 and 3, data are separated for β 600 and 1200 seconds respectively.

Table 2. Summarized analyses results of all simulations.

Number of Vehicles	α	β	Fleet Total Distance (km)	Total Empty Distance (km)	Empty Ratio	Total Passenger Distance Traveled (km)	Occupancy ratio	Mean Wait time (seconds)	Mean in Vehicle Travel Time (seconds)	Mean Total Travel Time (seconds)	Rejection Rate (%)	Mean driven distance by each vehicle (km)
Private cars 25,000	-	-	422,007	-	-	-	-	0		655	-	16.8
750	1.25	600	234,541	38,098	0.16	331,346	1.41	353	895	1,248	17.23	313
	1.5	600	223,817	33,029	0.15	369,643	1.65	375	1,008	1,383	15.90	298
	1.75	600	214,507	29,417	0.14	404,697	1.89	389	1,120	1,509	15.05	286
	1.25	1200	206,867	25,095	0.12	447,264	2.16	404	1,258	1,662	14.19	276
	1.5	1200	202,418	23,488	0.12	481,908	2.38	412	1,370	1,781	13.94	270
	1.75	1200	198,335	21,952	0.11	518,723	2.62	419	1,476	1,895	13.12	264
1000	1.25	600	266,591	44,997	0.17	379,529	1.42	342	907	1,248	11.22	267
	1.5	600	253,745	39,650	0.16	419,424	1.65	365	1,017	1,382	10.11	254
	1.75	600	243,087	35,293	0.15	460,422	1.89	382	1,129	1,511	9.14	243
	1.25	1200	234,543	30,947	0.13	504,024	2.15	397	1,263	1,660	8.60	235
	1.5	1200	228,226	28,249	0.12	545,223	2.39	405	1,374	1,780	7.91	228
	1.75	1200	222,416	25,849	0.12	584,137	2.63	413	1,483	1,896	7.46	222
1250	1.25	600	289,962	48,861	0.17	417,086	1.44	330	918	1,247	7.07	232
	1.5	600	276,758	43,360	0.16	460,900	1.67	356	1,027	1,383	5.93	221
	1.75	600	261,571	37,267	0.14	500,990	1.92	373	1,141	1,514	5.55	209
	1.25	1200	252,823	32,931	0.13	547,365	2.17	389	1,273	1,662	4.86	202
	1.5	1200	245,343	30,371	0.12	590,233	2.41	400	1,384	1,783	4.35	196
	1.75	1200	237,883	27,415	0.12	628,410	2.64	408	1,488	1,896	4.04	190
1500	1.25	600	307,691	51,235	0.17	447,112	1.45	324	928	1,252	4.38	205
	1.5	600	291,578	45,488	0.16	488,308	1.67	351	1,038	1,389	3.69	194
	1.75	600	279,192	41,140	0.15	533,920	1.91	369	1,149	1,518	2.72	186
	1.25	1200	267,163	36,068	0.14	579,671	2.17	386	1,281	1,667	2.37	178
	1.5	1200	259,112	33,334	0.13	623,513	2.41	395	1,391	1,787	1.94	173
	1.75	1200	251,663	30,643	0.12	664,538	2.64	405	1,495	1,900	1.48	168
2000	1.25	600	323,490	51,609	0.16	479,900	1.48	309	942	1,252	1.42	162
	1.5	600	301,823	44,176	0.15	516,558	1.71	336	1,048	1,384	1.17	151
	1.75	600	284,109	37,868	0.13	556,536	1.96	356	1,156	1,512	0.87	142
	1.25	1200	271,917	33,050	0.12	602,803	2.22	374	1,288	1,662	0.71	136
	1.5	1200	262,269	30,914	0.12	641,691	2.45	386	1,395	1,781	0	131
	1.75	1200	253,390	27,934	0.11	681,007	2.69	395	1,497	1,893	0	127
3000	1.25	600	326,553	46,391	0.14	498,100	1.53	293	953	1,247	0	109
	1.5	600	303,117	39,085	0.13	533,241	1.76	323	1,059	1,382	0	101
	1.75	600	283,492	33,860	0.12	568,075	2.00	344	1,164	1,509	0	94
	1.25	1200	269,119	28,723	0.11	609,570	2.27	363	1,291	1,655	0	90
	1.5	1200	258,265	26,482	0.10	646,193	2.50	376	1,398	1,774	0	86
	1.75	1200	248,277	24,313	0.10	679,360	2.74	389	1,496	1,885	0	83
5000	1.25	600	309,840	30,759	0.10	500,221	1.61	281	959	1,240	0	62
	1.5	600	289,081	26,110	0.09	534,662	1.85	312	1,062	1,374	0	58
	1.75	600	268,349	20,778	0.08	567,554	2.11	334	1,165	1,499	0	54
	1.25	1200	255,105	17,052	0.07	607,644	2.38	353	1,290	1,643	0	51
	1.5	1200	243,476	14,800	0.06	643,452	2.64	366	1,395	1,761	0	49
	1.75	1200	234,206	12,654	0.05	678,561	2.90	378	1,494	1,873	0	47
7000	1.25	600	297,822	19,600	0.07	502,651	1.69	268	963	1,231	0	43
	1.5	600	276,005	16,045	0.06	534,879	1.94	300	1,065	1,365	0	39
	1.75	600	257,390	12,304	0.05	566,861	2.20	322	1,167	1,489	0	37
	1.25	1200	244,763	9,029	0.04	606,769	2.48	343	1,289	1,632	0	35
	1.5	1200	235,190	7,692	0.03	642,676	2.73	357	1,392	1,749	0	34
	1.75	1200	225,872	6,598	0.03	673,837	2.98	369	1,487	1,856	0	32

Table 3. Summarized analyses results for β 600 seconds and Private cars scenario.

Number of Vehicles	α	β	Fleet Total Distance (km)	Total Empty Distance (km)	Empty Ratio	Total Passenger Distance Traveled (km)	Occupancy ratio	Mean Wait time (seconds)	Mean in Vehicle Travel Time (seconds)	Mean Total Travel Time (seconds)	Rejection Rate (%)	Mean driven distance by each vehicle (km)
Private cars 25,000	-	-	422,007	-	-	-	-	0	-	655	-	16.8
750	1.25	600	234,541	38,098	0.16	331,346	1.41	353	895	1,248	17.23	313
	1.5	600	223,817	33,029	0.15	369,643	1.65	375	1,008	1,383	15.90	298
	1.75	600	214,507	29,417	0.14	404,697	1.89	389	1,120	1,509	15.05	286
1000	1.25	600	266,591	44,997	0.17	379,529	1.42	342	907	1,248	11.22	267
	1.5	600	253,745	39,650	0.16	419,424	1.65	365	1,017	1,382	10.11	254
	1.75	600	243,087	35,293	0.15	460,422	1.89	382	1,129	1,511	9.14	243
1250	1.25	600	289,962	48,861	0.17	417,086	1.44	330	918	1,247	7.07	232
	1.5	600	276,758	43,360	0.16	460,900	1.67	356	1,027	1,383	5.93	221
	1.75	600	261,571	37,267	0.14	500,990	1.92	373	1,141	1,514	5.55	209
1500	1.25	600	307,691	51,235	0.17	447,112	1.45	324	928	1,252	4.38	205
	1.5	600	291,578	45,488	0.16	488,308	1.67	351	1,038	1,389	3.69	194
	1.75	600	279,192	41,140	0.15	533,920	1.91	369	1,149	1,518	2.72	186
2000	1.25	600	323,490	51,609	0.16	479,900	1.48	309	942	1,252	1.42	162
	1.5	600	301,823	44,176	0.15	516,558	1.71	336	1,048	1,384	1.17	151
	1.75	600	284,109	37,868	0.13	556,536	1.96	356	1,156	1,512	0.87	142
3000	1.25	600	326,553	46,391	0.14	498,100	1.53	293	953	1,247	0	109
	1.5	600	303,117	39,085	0.13	533,241	1.76	323	1,059	1,382	0	101
	1.75	600	283,492	33,860	0.12	568,075	2.00	344	1,164	1,509	0	94
5000	1.25	600	309,840	30,759	0.10	500,221	1.61	281	959	1,240	0	62
	1.5	600	289,081	26,110	0.09	534,662	1.85	312	1,062	1,374	0	58
	1.75	600	268,349	20,778	0.08	567,554	2.11	334	1,165	1,499	0	54
7000	1.25	600	297,822	19,600	0.07	502,651	1.69	268	963	1,231	0	43
	1.5	600	276,005	16,045	0.06	534,879	1.94	300	1,065	1,365	0	39
	1.75	600	257,390	12,304	0.05	566,861	2.20	322	1,167	1,489	0	37

Table 4. Summarized analyses results for β 1200 seconds and Private cars scenario.

Number of Vehicles	α	β	Fleet Total Distance (km)	Total Empty Distance (km)	Empty Ratio	Total Passenger Distance Traveled (km)	Occupancy ratio	Mean Wait time (seconds)	Mean in Vehicle Travel Time (seconds)	Mean Total Travel Time (seconds)	Rejection Rate (%)	Mean driven distance by each vehicle (km)
Private cars 25,000	-	-	422,007	-	-	-	-	0	-	655	-	16.8
750	1.25	1200	206,867	25,095	0.12	447,264	2.16	404	1,258	1,662	14.19	276
	1.5	1200	202,418	23,488	0.12	481,908	2.38	412	1,370	1,781	13.94	270
	1.75	1200	198,335	21,952	0.11	518,723	2.62	419	1,476	1,895	13.12	264
1000	1.25	1200	234,543	30,947	0.13	504,024	2.15	397	1,263	1,660	8.60	235
	1.5	1200	228,226	28,249	0.12	545,223	2.39	405	1,374	1,780	7.91	228
	1.75	1200	222,416	25,849	0.12	584,137	2.63	413	1,483	1,896	7.46	222
1250	1.25	1200	252,823	32,931	0.13	547,365	2.17	389	1,273	1,662	4.86	202
	1.5	1200	245,343	30,371	0.12	590,233	2.41	400	1,384	1,783	4.35	196
	1.75	1200	237,883	27,415	0.12	628,410	2.64	408	1,488	1,896	4.04	190
1500	1.25	1200	267,163	36,068	0.14	579,671	2.17	386	1,281	1,667	2.37	178
	1.5	1200	259,112	33,334	0.13	623,513	2.41	395	1,391	1,787	1.94	173
	1.75	1200	251,663	30,643	0.12	664,538	2.64	405	1,495	1,900	1.48	168
2000	1.25	1200	271,917	33,050	0.12	602,803	2.22	374	1,288	1,662	0.71	136
	1.5	1200	262,269	30,914	0.12	641,691	2.45	386	1,395	1,781	0	131
	1.75	1200	253,390	27,934	0.11	681,007	2.69	395	1,497	1,893	0	127
3000	1.25	1200	269,119	28,723	0.11	609,570	2.27	363	1,291	1,655	0	90
	1.5	1200	258,265	26,482	0.10	646,193	2.50	376	1,398	1,774	0	86
	1.75	1200	248,277	24,313	0.10	679,360	2.74	389	1,496	1,885	0	83
5000	1.25	1200	255,105	17,052	0.07	607,644	2.38	353	1,290	1,643	0	51
	1.5	1200	243,476	14,800	0.06	643,452	2.64	366	1,395	1,761	0	49
	1.75	1200	234,206	12,654	0.05	678,561	2.90	378	1,494	1,873	0	47
7000	1.25	1200	244,763	9,029	0.04	606,769	2.48	343	1,289	1,632	0	35
	1.5	1200	235,190	7,692	0.03	642,676	2.73	357	1,392	1,749	0	34
	1.75	1200	225,872	6,598	0.03	673,837	2.98	369	1,487	1,856	0	32

7.2.1. Fleet Total distance

Total kilometers driven by vehicles for different parameters are shown in the Figures 46 and 47. As can be seen there is an increasing trend then starts decreasing and the main reason for this fluctuation is due to number of served and rejected requests which result in different Total distances (rejection rates are explained in the next section). For β 600 the peak is for fleet size of 3000 and for β 1200 the peak is for the fleet size of 2000. Comparing Ridepooling vs Private cars scenario, for the β 600 and α 1.25 there is at least a decrease of almost 22% and for β 1200 and α 1.25 there is at least a decrease of 35% in the vehicle kilometers traveled.

Figure 46. Fleet total distance for different fleet sizes for β 600.

Figure 47. Fleet total distance for different fleet sizes for β 1200.

7.2.2. Rejection Rate

Rejection ratios, which are calculated by dividing Rejected number of requests to Served number of Requests, are shown in the Figures 48 and 49 for β 600 and 1200 respectively.

As can be seen there is a decreasing trend by increasing fleet size and for the fleet size of 2000, an appropriate situation is reached with rejection rates of almost 1% for β 600 and almost 0% for β 1200 and for larger fleet sizes, rejection ratios are all 0%.

Figure 48. Rejection ratios for different fleet sizes for β 600.

Figure 49. Rejection ratios for different fleet sizes for β 1200.

7.2.3. Empty Ratio

Empty ratios, which are calculated by dividing Total empty distance driven by vehicles to the Total distance driven by vehicles, are shown in the Figures 50 and 51 for β 600 and 1200 respectively. After almost all requests are served, fleet size 2000 onwards, by increasing the fleet size the empty ratio decreases, main reason is because there are more vehicles distributed in the city so they are closer to passengers and less distance is needed to be driven to reach them while being empty.

Figure 50. Empty ratios for different fleet sizes for β 600.

Figure 51. Empty ratios for different fleet sizes for β 1200.

7.2.4. Occupancy ratio

Occupancy ratios, which are calculated by dividing Total passenger distance traveled by Fleet total distance driven, are shown in the Figures 52 and 53 for β 600 and 1200 respectively. As can be seen in both figures, there is an increasing trend in Occupancy ratios by increasing fleet size because as explained in the previous section due to higher distribution of cars in the city, active vehicles perform more efficiently.

Figure 52. Occupancy ratios for different fleet sizes for β 600.

Figure 53. Occupancy ratios for different fleet sizes for β 1200.

7.2.5. Occupancy situation

In the following figures, 54 to 61, Occupancy situation for different fleet sizes and parameters are shown. For example, for the fleet size 750 and α 1.25 and β 600, almost 16% of the distance driven the vehicles are empty and 37% of the distance driven they traveled with only 1 passenger and so on. By increasing fleet size, α and β , occupancies are improved.

Figure 54. Occupancy situation for the fleet size 750.

Figure 55. Occupancy situation for the fleet size 1000.

Figure 56. Occupancy situation for the fleet size 1250.

Figure 57. Occupancy situation for the fleet size 1500.

Figure 58. Occupancy situation for the fleet size 2000.

Figure 59. Occupancy situation for the fleet size 3000.

Figure 60. Occupancy situation for the fleet size 5000.

Figure 61. Occupancy situation for the fleet size 7000.

7.2.6. Mean Waiting time

In the Figures 62 and 63, average waiting time of passengers are represented and as can be seen by increasing fleet size this value is decreased. As an example, for fleet size of 750, α 1.25 and β 600, this value is 309 seconds (5:09 minutes) and for β 1200 this value is 374 seconds (6:14 minutes).

Figure 62. Mean waiting time for different fleet sizes for β 600.

Figure 63. Mean waiting time for different fleet sizes for β 1200.

7.2.7. Mean Total Travel Time

In the Figures 64 and 65, average total travel times, which include Waiting time and In vehicle travel time, are shown. For example, for fleet size 2000, α 1.25 and β 600, total travel time is 1,252 seconds (20:52 minutes) and for β 1200 it is 1,662 seconds (27:42 minutes). That is to mention, mean total travel time in Private cars scenario was 655 seconds (10:55 minutes) without considering required time to look for parking spot.

Figure 64. Mean total travel time for different fleet sizes for β 600.

Figure 65. Mean total travel time for different fleet sizes for β 1200.

7.2.8. Mean driven distance by each vehicle

In the Figures 66 and 67, average driven distance by each vehicle is shown and as can be seen by increasing fleet sizes this value is decreased.

Figure 66. Mean driven distance per vehicle for different fleet sizes for β 600.

Figure 67. Mean driven distance per vehicle for different fleet sizes for β 1200.

8. Conclusion

In this work it was tried to show the possible effects of replacing private cars with autonomous ridepooling system in Karlsruhe, Germany. By using an agent-based simulation software, MATsim, it was found out by introducing a ridepooling provider, using 6 seat electric autonomous vans, the number of cars can be reduced up to 92%, 2,000 instead of 25,000 vehicles, and almost all trips of the same population can be served and even the driven distance by vehicles can be decreased for minimum of 23%, depending on the different parameters. This replacement would result in an increase of travel time for at least 10 minutes for passengers, but that is to mention in the simulation for the base case scenario, that people used their own private cars, required time for looking for parking spot is not considered. Another important factor which is improved is the occupancy ratio, minimum increase of 48%, compared to base case scenario.

All the above-mentioned improvements could lead to reduction in energy consumption and emissions, lower need of parking areas on the streets, decline in traffic congestions and lower costs for passengers.

Further studies could focus on multimodal choice mode that people would be allowed to choose among different mobility options.

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